

STUDY ON THE INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL FACTORS INVOLVED IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF DISEASES DETERMINED BY CANDIDA GENUS AND SPECIES

O. Moroianu,

Doctoral School, University "Ovidius" of Constanta, Romania

N. Popescu,

Central Medical Iowemed from Constanta, Romania

L. Gurgas,

Faculty of Medicine, University "Ovidius" of Constanta

N. Rosoiu,

Academy of Romanian Scientists, Bucharest

Emeritus Professor, Faculty of Medicine, University "Ovidius" of Constanta

O. Azis

Faculty of Medicine, University "Ovidius" of Constanta

Ovidius Clinical Hospital, Constanta, Romania

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Abstract

The paper aims to systematize the information related to the etiopathogenesis of cutaneous-mucosal candidiasis, with the aim of highlighting the most effective prophylactic and therapeutic indications of these conditions.

Keywords: Candida albicans, Colonies, Sabouroud, CHROMagar, API20C and API 32C

Abbreviations: a = albicans, t= tropicalis, k=krusei, l=lusitaniae, g=glabrata, p=parapsilosis; chl=chlamydospor; h- hour; µg - micrograme

Introduction

Due to the high frequency of cases detected with different evolutionary forms of candidiasis, it can be appreciated that the entire population is contaminated, at least with Candida spores, but the pathology is triggered when imbalances appear in the body. The most important species are:

- Candida albicans
- Candida famata
- Candida glabrata
- Candida guilliermondii
- Candida krusei
- Candida lusitaniae

- Candida parapsilosis
- Candida tropicalis
- Candida norvegiensis
- Candida dubliniensis.

The main species of the genus Candida is Candida Albicans.

The genus belongs to the family Cryptococaceae, from Deuteromycete, heterogeneous genus, characterized by globular, oval or elongated cells or blastospores (blastoconidia) that reproduce by lateral budding. Most species form pseudohyphae (1).

Figure 1(a, b). Yeasts: *Candida albicans* - budding and production of pseudofilaments (2)

Candida spp. is ubiquitous in nature, being present in small numbers in the normal flora of the digestive, genital and skin mucous membranes.

- It multiplies by budding (bud → daughter cell or blastospore, by the elongation of which pseudo-filaments or pseudohyphae are formed). *Candida* exhibits

3-4 μm yeast cells, usually showing single budding. Pseudohyphae are 5-10 μm , have thinned ends and remain attached. True hyphae if present have parallel walls and are septate. If pseudohyphae or nests of blastoconidia are observed on smears from pathological products, it is an indication of the fact that their way of life is no longer saprophytic but parasitic.

- The colonies are white, creamy, large and develop at 28-30 °C after 48-72h (maximum 5 days).
- Cultures for fungi are done on special media, such as Sabouraud (Sabouraud dextrose agar), for nor-

Figure 2. *Candida*: morphological aspects a = *albicans*, t=*tropicalis*, k=*krusei*, l=*lusitanae*, g=*glabrata*, p=*parapsilosis*; chl=*chlamydo-spore*

b. Biochemical tests:

– CHROMagar *Candida* allows the presumptive identification of some *Candida* species using color reactions in specialized environments.

– API20C and API 32C are miniaturized and automated galleries of biochemical reactions (assimilation of some substrates) that determine biochemical profiles on the basis of which several yeast species can be identified. Antifungigram Antifungal sensitivity testing (antifungigram) can be performed by

- the diffusion method,
- E-test or
- the dilution method (microdilutions).

The diffusimetric method uses RPMI agar culture medium, the standard inoculum of 0.5 Mc Farland and discs with antifungal substances (Amphotericin B 10 μg , Ketoconazole 15 μg , Itraconazole 8 μg , Fluconazole 25 μg , Voriconazole 1.0 μg , 5-Fluorocytosine 1 and 10 μg E-test uses strips impregnated with antifungal substances in decreasing concentrations, the MIC can also be determined. The indicated culture medium is RPMI agar with glucose.

• The dilution method is used to determine the MIC, and the medium used is RPMI broth. There are commercial kits for antifungigrams by the microdilution method

• Other species are: *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida kefyr*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida parapsilosis*, *Candida glabrata*, *Candida famata*, *Candida guilliermondii*.

• Candidiasis can be located at different levels: skin, oral cavity, gastrointestinal tract, genitourinary tract (3). The site and mechanism by which antifungals exert their effects are specific to each class and are important for establishing the therapeutic strategy (4,5).

• Recent studies conducted in Europe and the USA highlight the increase in the incidence of nosocomial fungal infections, with a worrying mortality rate

that can reach 40-70% of cases. Fungimias due to various species of *Candida* are ranked 4th in incidence in the list of systemic infections associated with medical care, after bacteremias with species from the genera *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Enterococcus* (6,7).

Species identification

a. Morphological characters: species of the genus *Candida* can be identified based on morphological characters, germination test: filaments are produced from yeast cells after 2-3 h of incubation.

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• The decrease in the frequency of isolation of the *Candida albicans* species and the increase in the incidence of fungi with non-*albicans* species (*C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. krusei*) represent a worldwide trend. Thus, the pattern of resistance to antifungals is particular, different from that of *C. albicans* strains, in general, more sensitive (7).

• Candidiasis is a disease produced by *Candida albicans* that lives saprophyte in the digestive tract of a healthy person, being in perfect balance with the intestinal flora.

• Factors favoring infection include prolonged antibiotic therapy, immunosuppressive therapy, diabetes mellitus, AIDS, use of contraceptives, antitrichomoniasis treatment.

• In relation to the location, the clinical aspects are different. Thus, localization at the level of the oral mucosa causes erosive lesions or whitish deposits, removable, associated with the sensation of burning, xerostomia.

• Localization on the vulvo-vaginal mucosa produces inflammation, erythema, itching, burning sensation, purulent vaginal secretions with a fetid odor (8).

• In *Candida auris* infestation to be caught: liver, spleen, central nervous system-CNS, muscles, joints, bones and eyes. The evolution is usually severe, *Candida auris* being multi-resistant to antifungals and the disease usually affecting an organism with a greatly reduced or even abolished defense capacity (immune mechanisms) (9).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study took place between August 1-31, 2017 at the Iowemed Medical Center - Medcover in Constanța on a 26-year-old patient who presented to the medical office with a condition in the vaginal area.

Results

Patient M.C., aged 26, complained of discomfort in the vaginal area, specifically itching, itching and unpleasant smell. Samples were taken from the patient. *Candida albicans* was isolated in vaginal discharge. We put samples for analysis on petri dishes that were left for 72 h at a thermostat at 37 °C to make observations.

Figure 3. Colonies of *Candida albicans* 24 h after seeding

Figure 4. Colonies of *Candida albicans* at 72h after seeding, sensitive to Amphotericin B, Nystatin, Flucytosine, Econazole, Miconazole, Fluconazole In the present study we used a candida identification system called Candifast.

Discussions

(a)

(b)

Figure 5(a, b). *Candifast identification system Discussion Candifast is an identification kit based on fermentation tests and determining the presence of urease.*

Copper and zinc have a role in boosting immunity and increasing fertility (4); in general, essential oils have the property of interfering with the function of the lipid bilayer in the cell membrane, altering its functions and disrupting the activity of enzymes and genetic resources in fungal cells (10).

This test can identify 8 species of *Candida* and can specify whether the tested strain belongs to the genera *Trichosporon*, *Geotrichum* or *Rodothorula*, but without being able to specify the genus or species.

Candifast also contains a sensitivity test kit. The following strains of *Candida* can be identified:

- *Candida albicans*
- *Candida tropicalis*
- *Candida glabrata*
- *Candida krusei*

The identification kit is based on:

- Assimilation tests
- Enzyme tests
- Morphological

Following the determinations / laboratory tests, the *Candida albicans* species was identified at the patient in question

Following the laboratory determinations, the patient was proposed to normalize the vaginal pH/ alkalize the vaginal mucosa, i.e. frequent washings with 2% sodium bicarbonate solutions, the administration of essential vitamins, as well as avoiding the use of antibiotics throughout the treatment. This is all the more so since the resistance to antibiotics is continuously increasing (11). There is clear evidence showing a direct relationship between the consumption of antibiotics and the resistance developed by microbial agents (12). After a period of 14 days, patient MC returned to the laboratory, where we found complete healing following laboratory tests.

Prophylactic and therapeutic indications

It is considered that the prevention of the occurrence of candidiasis can be achieved by:

- alkalizing techniques of integumentary and mucous surfaces (for example with solutions containing sodium bicarbonate);
- maintaining the immunological balance by using eubiotics and vitamin complexes;
- ensuring the immunological status by ensuring hours of physical and mental rest and a balanced dietary intake of nutritional principles and essential vitamins;
- avoiding general antibiotic therapy for periods longer than 5-7 days.

Thus, the patient was advised to normalize the vaginal pH/alkalize the vaginal mucosa, i.e. frequent washes with sodium bicarbonate solutions 2 %, the administration of essential vitamins, as well as to avoid the use of antibiotics throughout the treatment. After a period of 14 days, patient MC returned to the control and it was found, following the laboratory tests, that she was completely cured.

Conclusions

The methods by which candidiasis prophylaxis is carried out can be successfully recommended for therapeutic purposes, even without medicinal agents.

The success of the prophylaxis, but also of the therapy of candidiasis of the mucous membranes and integuments, consists in ensuring an optimal immunological status.

Periodic monitoring of the components of the skin microbiome and mucous membranes, through laboratory investigations, can ensure the normality of these organs, through the timely application of prophylactic and at the same time therapeutic indications.

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